

Citation for the Presentation of the
2013 ICPE Medal to

The International Young Physicists' Tournament

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The ICPE Medal for 2013 is awarded to the International Young Physicists' Tournament (IYPT) in recognition of its inspiring and wide-ranging contribution to physics education that has touched many lives and countries, over the past 25 years.

IYPT is a team-oriented competition between secondary school students. It is sometimes referred to as the Physics World Cup. Each of its annual Tournaments consists of a series of "disputes" in which competing teams present and defend their previously prepared reports on challenging, open-ended physics problems that are set and publicised well before the week-long Tournament begins. The members of each team take on the roles of Reporters, Opponents and Reviewers throughout the successive rounds of the competition, thus gaining insight into the nature of scientific debate and the process of peer review. The outcome of each round and hence, ultimately, of the whole Tournament is decided by a panel of expert judges.

The idea behind the IYPT originated in the former Soviet Union, and the first Tournaments were held there, starting in 1988. Since then the movement has been successful in attracting increasing international interest and support. In 1994 the Tournament moved to Groningen in the Netherlands, and from there to other European cities. In 2004 the host city was Brisbane in Australia, and since then IYPT has become a truly global event with host cities in South Korea, China, Iran and, this year, Chinese Taipei. Each Tournament now involves hundreds of participants, young and old, novice and expert but also of great importance are the many thousands of individuals taking part worldwide through national heats and preparatory events.

IYPT has become a major landmark in the international physics education calendar, and ICPE is delighted to recognize its influence and celebrate its success with the award of the 2013 ICPE Medal for outstanding contributions to international physics education.

Robert Lambourne
Chairman of ICPE